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Sociocultural Factors of China's Managerial Model of Development

KEYWORDS

Communist Party of China,
multi-party system,
national identity,
social stability,
sociocultural programs,
management strategy

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of the study is determined by the importance of analyzing China's management strategy, including the use of sociocultural resources, for understanding its domestic and foreign policy. Research on the influence of sociocultural factors helps to understand the specifics of the Chinese development model.

The study is aimed at studying the sociocultural content of the global reform policy of modern China.

Materials and methods. When studying the topic, scientific publications in the fields of sociology, cultural studies, political science, and economics published in peer-reviewed journals, were utilized. The research employed the following methods: systemic, typological, comparative, inductive, descriptive, and others.

Results. The "Civil Service Law" is an important legal resource regulating the activities of state personnel. Within the multi-party system with the leading role of the Communist Party of China (CPC), a table of parties with their logos, leaders, and influence in society was created. Consultations involving all stakeholders ensure the adoption of well-founded reforms, which is considered an important managerial resource alongside personnel policy. The sociocultural aspect of the strategy is associated with the construction of socialism with Chinese characteristics, aimed at improving the living standards and well-being of the people. The multifaceted nature of the resources of the management strategy in the economic, cultural, scientific, political, and ideological spheres is emphasized in the research.

Conclusion. The success of China's management strategy is due to its sociocultural content, which satisfies the most important human needs and contributes to the country's accelerated development. Important resources of the strategy are the legal and political systems, the scientific substantiation of reforms, the training of qualified personnel, and the ideological foundation of socialism with Chinese characteristics. The image of the CPC as a leader of modernization ensures social stability in the face of international threats of disintegration. Overall, the resources of China's management strategy are multifaceted and are implemented in domestic and foreign policy, economy, culture, science, and technology.

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INTRODUCTION

The relevance of the study is determined by the fact that understanding the specifics of China's management strategy, including the use of sociocultural resources, is important for analyzing its domestic and foreign policy. China combines elements of a market economy with state regulation and preserves its cultural traditions. Studying how sociocultural factors influence management strategy helps to understand the specifics of the Chinese development model.

The scientific interest lies in a systematic approach to examining the resources of the management strategy, which include legal, political, ideological, personnel, and other components.

The study is aimed at examining the sociocultural content of the global reform policy of modern China.

The novelty of the research consists in the classification of factors ensuring the ideological program of building the world's only major socialist power.

In order to address the stated goal, the "Civil Service Law" is cited, which implements the strategy of "the Party overseeing personnel". Multi-party cooperation within the framework of the Chinese People's Political Consultative Conference (CPPCC) serves as a political resource for a unified and coordinated national development course. Effective governance at the state level is ensured not only by the scientific substantiation of decisions made but also by the existence of a nationwide system for training and retraining personnel.

The sociocultural content of modern China's management strategy is studied within the context of the idea of building socialism with Chinese characteristics. The research emphasizes that the modernized ideology in the People's Republic of China (PRC) traces back to the theory of scientific communism and the meaning of Soviet ideologemes such as "raising the standard of living" and "improving the people's welfare", which are implemented through a system of measures in economy and politics, culture and science, education and medicine.

The systematization of information presented at the research leads to the assertion that the effective resources of the management strategy are the legal and political structures, the scientific substantiation of economic reforms, the creation of a competent body of civil servants, and adherence to the ideological postulates of the theory of socialism with Chinese characteristics. The stated topic is of not only

scientific but also practical interest in the context of searching for possible paths for further civilizational development.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

When studying the topic, scientific publications and studies in the field of sociology, cultural studies, political science, and economics, dedicated to analyzing the sociocultural context in China, were utilized. The works were published in peer-reviewed periodicals such as Agriculture and Human Values, Regional Studies, Humanities and Social Sciences Communications, Comparative Economic Studies, Empirical Economics, The Journal of Chinese Sociology, and others.

A systemic method is employed in the analysis of conceptual aspects of the main resources of the management strategy. The study of their sociocultural content, based on the application of a typological approach, allows for the identification of legislative, political, personnel, scientific, and ideological types of resources. Abstraction from the criteria for qualitative assessment of personnel potential provides an opportunity to focus on the issue of the Communist Party of China (CPC) ensuring a controlling role in management policy during the phase of global transformations. The comparative method yields an effective result in compiling a table for structuring China's political system, which is characterized by multi-party cooperation. The inductive nature of the research allows for a conclusion about the conditions for the effectiveness of the management strategy, based on an understanding of the decision-making mechanism and the state system for personnel training and retraining. A descriptive method is implemented in enumerating activities with sociocultural content that form the basis of the management strategy. An analytical-descriptive approach facilitates the examination of sociocultural programs from the perspective of their content. The method of synthesis is applied in defining legal and political, social and ideological resources to characterize the multifaceted management strategy of contemporary China.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Management problems are actualized at the modern civilizational stage, in connection with the need to coordinate dichotomous trends that manifest themselves in social and technological terms. It is no coincidence that monographs appear based on a comparative analysis of the experience of countries with different socio-

cultural realities, different economic and energy potential, in particular Russia and China [1]. Scientists study the problems of changes in management processes in connection with the development of the digital economy and assess the prospects for the redistribution of management functions [2].

Currently, global challenges include the decline in the working-age population against the backdrop of increasing life expectancy, as well as the nature of education in the context of the widespread use of artificial intelligence. The article by M.Y. Zakharov [3] is devoted to the sociocultural foundation of modern personnel training for public administration in the PRC, and to understanding the dynamics and prospects of the professionalization of management education in contemporary China. The theoretical interest lies in comprehending the personal status in real and virtual communicative dimensions [4].

In the era of digitalization and the use of artificial intelligence, the role of civil servants in implementing management strategies in the fields of culture [5–7], economy [8; 9], and politics is increasing. Scholars are addressing issues of state regulation of the civil service [10], the study of normative documents of a state-party nature [11], the specifics of the transformation of China's civil service under new economic conditions [12], and comparative analyses of the civil service systems in China and Russia [13].

Of scientific interest is the experience of creating political stability in China, which is ensured by the leading role of the CPC [14–17]. China's progressive development in the modern era is based on the official theory of socialism with Chinese characteristics, which is interpreted by various specialists [18–20].

Z. Zhang notes that since the XVIII Congress of the CPC in 2012, Secretary General Xi Jinping has put forward the historical task of building a socialist political economy with Chinese characteristics [21].

Social stability in China is ensured through strong government control, economic growth, infrastructure development, and measures to maintain order.

R. Zhang et al. emphasize that Social Stability Risk Assessment (SSRA) has become a key policy tool for evaluating potential risks of large-scale development projects across all sectors in China. In order to maintain high economic competitiveness among provinces, SSRA policies should be structured around addressing social stability issues and tackling specific sectoral challenges (e.g., pollution) within a particular industry (such as natural resources). The scholars emphasize the necessity of a dual objective: pursuing economic reforms while maintaining a harmonious society [22].

Y. Ma and C. Sun observe that the trade liberalization process represents a deepening and refinement of China's institutions, which is certain to have a profound impact on social trust. According to their research, import trade liberalization enhances social trust among Chinese residents primarily through the channel of improved institutional quality [23].

H. Xu et al. investigate the mediating role of social capital in rural China, where rapid economic growth coexists with gradual yet fundamental social changes. The authors find that "trust" has a positive effect on the "happiness" of rural residents and on "social capital". The mediating influence of social capital is significant for rural residents aged 30 and above who live in areas with high market competition [24].

M. Liang et al. analyze the Chinese model of automated emotional labor, which differs from the commercialized emotional labor model. In this new model, consumers (clients) and workers are equal and mutually beneficial interactive agents, and emotional labor no longer serves as a spear for capital but instead becomes a shield for workers against issues in the labor process [25].

Q. Wang and B. S. Nayak point out that China's economic growth rate has begun to slow in recent years. The authors attribute this to existing regional disparities and uneven resource distribution. They argue that the state should establish a scientific and standardized system of fiscal decentralization, reform the uniform evaluation system, and optimize administrative expenditures to promote balanced regional development [26].

According to S. Kışmari, lifestyle, lack of religious freedom, human rights violations, censorship, and the single-party system demonstrate that Chinese citizens live under conditions different from those in the West. The fundamental principles of the state have remained unchanged: Marxism-Leninism-Maoism, party leadership over the state, the dictatorship of the proletariat, and the socialist path. The role of the Communist Party remains decisive in China, as it controls all three branches of power: executive, legislative, and judicial [27].

L. Linyan and C. Boqing study the phenomenon of "hope" present in Chinese society. The authors reveal the objective context for the formation of hope by illustrating structural changes in Chinese society since the reform and opening-up period. The Chinese Dream is examined from the perspective of supplying social meaning and building a community of hope [28].

Thus, numerous researchers examine various aspects of China's socio-economic development. Authors note that trade liberalization contributes to strengthening

institutional trust and developing social capital. Scholars also highlight the slowdown in economic growth due to regional imbalances and the need for fiscal system reforms to achieve balanced development.

RESULTS

Legislative and political resources of the management strategy

An important social and legal resource of the management strategy is the regulation of personnel activities, which is enshrined in the “Civil Service Law”. The approval of its latest version by such an authoritative body as the Standing Committee of the National People’s Congress underscores the exceptional importance of managerial resources in ensuring the success of the global civilizational reforms being performed in China.

The provisions of the Law are based on the postulates of the Constitution regarding the leading role of the CPC, popular representation in all power structures of administrative-territorial subordination, and local executive authorities. An important principle of the Civil Service Law is the correspondence of the position to qualification requirements, which provides for various mechanisms for incentivizing civil servants.

The Civil Service Law guarantees the implementation of the management strategy expressed in the thesis that “the party is responsible for personnel”. In the context of global sociocultural reforms, the principles of equality, openness, and competitiveness become goal-setting for creating a corps of civil servants capable of developing socialist ideology.

The social stability of Chinese society is ensured by the activities of legal parties based on multi-party cooperation. The goal of the CPPCC is to develop a unified, agreed-upon course and prevent opposition.

The Communist Party is not the only party in China: the political system is characterized by the presence of eight officially registered so-called democratic parties. They are part of the state advisory body, the CPPCC, whose activities are based on ideological unity – socialism with Chinese characteristics – and recognition of the leading role of the CPC. The principle of multi-party cooperation is reflected in the Constitution of the PRC, which formulates the fundamental task of the country’s leadership: “to gradually achieve the modernization of industry, agriculture, national defense, and science and technology, and to promote the harmonious development of material, political, and spiritual culture” [29–35].

Representation in the country's highest legislative body and the number of registered parties operating in China attest to their popularity. The study proposes a developed informative table on the parties constituting the political resource of the management strategy.

Table 1

Parties in modern China

No	Name/ Year of establishment	Logo	Founder (lifespan, education)	Current leader (lifespan, education)	Membership size/ Number of seats in the NPC
1.	Communist Party of China 1921		Chen Duxiu (1879-1942), Universities in China (Zhejiang) and Japan. Li Dazhao (1889-1927) Waseda University, Japan.	Xi Jinping (b. 1953), General Secretary of the Central Committee (since 2012), Tsinghua University (Beijing)	98,000,000 members/ 108 seats
2.	Revolutionary Committee of the Kuomintang 1948		Li Jishen (1885-1959), Baoding Military Academy	Zhou Tenong (1938-2023), Chairman of the Central Committee, Peking University	131,000 members/ 5 seats
3.	China Democratic League 1941		Zhang Lan (1872-1955), education details unknown, served as President of Chengdu Normal Institute from 1928	Ding Zhongli (b. 1957), Zhejiang University	1,598,800 members/ 7 seats
4	China Association for Promoting Democracy (Mínjiàn) 1945		Gu Jiegang (1893-1980), Peking University	Hao Mingjin (b. 1956), Shandong Normal University, Northeast Normal University, China University of Political Science and Law	117,000 members/ 2 seats
5.	China Association for Promoting Democracy 1945		Ma Xulong (1885-1970), Professor at Peking University	Cai Dafeng (b. 1960) Tongji University	156,808 members/ 6 seats

6.	Chinese Peasants' and Workers' Democratic Party 1927		Deng Yanda (1895-1931), Baoding Military Academy	He Wei (b. 1955), Heilongjiang University of Chinese Medicine	177,900 members/ 6 seats
7.	Zhigongdang (China Zhi Gong Party) 1925		Situ Meitang (1872-1956)	Wan Gang (b. 1952) Northeast Forest University, Tongji University, Clausthal University of Technology	20,000 members/ 3 seats
8.	Jiusan Society 1946		Xu Deheng (1890-1990), politician, scholar, and educator	Wu Weihua (b. 1956) Rutgers University Shanxi University.	167,000 memers/ 6 seats
9.	Taiwan Democratic Self-Government League 1947		Members of the Communist Party of Taiwan	Lin Wenyi (b. 1944) Tsinghua University	3,000 members/ 3 seats

Scientific and personnel resources of the management strategy

Effective governance at the state level is ensured by the depth of analytical elaboration in decision-making and the establishment of a nationwide system for personnel training and professional development.

The first condition is met through the study of all current issues discussed in research centers operating under the CPC Central Committee and the State Council. The Development Research Center of the State Council of the People's Republic of China, which includes research institutes, foundations, and departments, serves as a developer of strategically important directions for progressive advancement. These entities study the current state and prospects of agriculture, macro- and microeconomics, human and natural resources, finance, and regional and market economies. The Center initiates international conferences and national forums on pressing issues of socio-economic reform in East Asia and China, as well as fundamental shifts in the axiological paradigm of modern civilization. Officially designated as the Ministry of Strategic Analysis, the Center provides theoretical

outcomes of its research, ensuring the scientific rigor of decisions made by the CPC Central Committee and the State Council.

It can be argued that systematic consultations with the active democratic parties under the leadership of the CPC guarantee the theoretical foundation of the current reform stage and serve as a key managerial resource stabilizing the political situation in the country.

The second condition for the effective performance of civil servants is the presence of an extensive network of organizations providing personnel training and the functioning of various forms of professional development.

The reform of institutions specializing in public administration, finance, and economics dates back to the beginning of the sociocultural transformations of Chinese society in the 1990s. Universities in these fields began operating within the framework of previously existing party schools. This educational reform in China is known as the “one institution, two names” program. The leading institution of this type is the National Academy of Governance, which was merged with the CPC Central Party School in 2018.

Thus, personnel policy, based on authoritarian discipline, high professionalism, and commitment to official ideology, is considered a crucial resource of the management strategy for the modernization of contemporary China.

Sociocultural content of the management strategy in contemporary China

At the turn of the 20th and 21st centuries, the goal of the management strategy has been the construction of socialism with Chinese characteristics, which retains the objectives of improving living standards and comprehensively enhancing the welfare of the Chinese people. The management strategy is implemented through a system of measures carried out in ideology and culture, as well as in social and economic policies.

The ideological foundation of China's contemporary modernization is the theory of socialism with Chinese characteristics. The task of creating an ideal society involves combining personal and public interests, developing the responsibility of each citizen and the creative potential of the entire people, and maintaining national identity at a stage characterized by a trend toward cultural homogenization.

Preserving national cultural distinctiveness, combined with high moral and ethical principles, aims to achieve a vanguard position in the contemporary world order.

Sociocultural programs involve improving the educational system and reducing material and social boundaries between strata, ensuring the comprehensive development of the individual.

The main economic vectors of contemporary reforms include ensuring the ability of Chinese goods to compete with similar products from recognized brands on the international stage, as well as achieving a leading position in certain manufacturing industries in the future.

The Chinese management strategy is based on the principle of the primacy of the individual, in contrast to the Western model, which focuses on economic development. The “Scientific Development Program” proposes the “Five Unified Coordinations”:

- Equal attention to urban and rural development. This sets the task of creating social infrastructure in rural areas and reducing the material disparity between rural and urban populations;
- Reducing disparities between western and eastern regions through the implementation of regional socio-economic projects;
- Equivalence of economic and sociocultural programs – funding for medical, educational, housing, and utility systems, as well as the economic and energy sectors;
- Coordination of policies on national identity and global economic dominance, improving the quality of export products through innovative technologies;
- Harmonization of relations between society and nature, adhering to a new type of industrialization that does not worsen the ecological environment.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The success of the management strategy in the PRC can be attributed to its sociocultural content, which addresses vital human needs and facilitates the country's accelerated civilizational development. The state simultaneously advances socially critical sectors such as healthcare, food security, and education, alongside socially significant innovative directions in science and economics, particularly energy and transportation infrastructure, artificial intelligence, communication, and digital technologies.

Effective resources of the management strategy include the legal and political system, scientifically grounded economic reforms, the establishment of a competent

corps of civil servants, and adherence to the ideological postulates of the theory of socialism with Chinese characteristics.

The image of the CPC as the organizer and leader of the course of civilizational modernization within a multi-party political system ensures social stability in the country amid existing international threats of disintegration.

Thus, the resources of contemporary China's management strategy exhibit a multi-vector spectrum of development, implemented in domestic and foreign policy, economic and cultural life, as well as scientific and technological domains.

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